

Sustainable Energy and Climate Policies in the Light of Changing Global and Regional Dynamics *(in Turkish)*

Theme: Energy, European Research Area and SSH Aspects

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Moderator: Erkan Erdil

Live Seminar Time and Date: 12:00-13:00 (Turkish time / GMT + 3)

Friday, May 27, 2022

Register at: <https://forms.gle/p6NP3w4K26BDYXye7>

Moderation: Prof. Dr. Erkan Erdil

Registration for live seminar closes at 20:00, Thursday, 26 May 2022: To receive the link to the live seminar you must register by 20:00, Thursday 26 May 2022.

Abstract: In the light of critical global transformations in the energy sector, this seminar evaluates the effects of the regional conflict and rivalry, which increased with the Russian invasion of Ukraine, and the reflections of these developments on Turkey. While approaching the issue with the perspective of energy security, the climate and sustainability dimensions of the issue are also taken into consideration.

Speaker:

Professor Yılmaz graduated from the International Relations Department of Bilkent University in 1993 as the Valedictorian. She received her M.A and Ph.D. from Princeton University, in 1995 and 2000, consecutively, specializing on Near Eastern Studies and International Relations. She conducted her post-doctoral Studies at Harvard University and was Visiting Professor at UCLA with a dual appointment at the Department of Public Policy, Luskin School of Public Affairs and the Luskin Center for Innovation (2016-2017 academic year). She held visiting faculty positions in the Center for Russian, East European and Eurasian Studies, Stanford University and the Center for International Studies, Princeton University. She received many national and international awards and grants. In 2008, she was granted the prestigious Distinguished Young Scientist Award of the Turkish Academy of Sciences and in 2016, she received the Koç University Outstanding Teaching Award. Professor Yılmaz teaches International Relations, Turkish Foreign Policy, Turkish-American Relations, Middle Eastern Politics, Politics of Former USSR and Central Asia, European Foreign and Security Policy, as well as Foreign Policy Analysis for Global Leaders in the Graduate School of Business and Political Economy of the Middle East and North Africa in the Global Network for Advanced Management (GNAM). Her recent research focuses on the international affairs of Eurasia and the Middle East, foreign policy analysis, Turkish foreign policy, international security and European security and foreign policy, energy and natural resource politics, Turkish-US-EU and Turkish-Russian relations. She has numerous publications in journals such as International Politics, Political Science Quarterly, Middle East Journal, Third World Quarterly, Middle Eastern Studies, Turkish Studies and Energy Research and Social Science. She has a recent book on Turkish-American Relations entitled Turkish-American Relations (1800-1952): Between the Stars, Stripes and the Crescent (2015) from Routledge Press International Relations Series.

About SolarTwins-TEKPOL Seminars: The path to a prosperous, sustainable, and secure Turkey includes a Clean Energy Transition (CET) and Green Economy Transition (GET). Many of the largest challenges to be solved to realize these transitions lie at the intersection of technology and policy. Some of these challenges are unique to a specific technology, while others are cross-cutting challenges that underpin the competitiveness of Turkey's Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem. This SolarTwins-TEKPOL Pizza Seminar series aims to provide a scientific forum to increase awareness of these challenges and contribute to the co-creation of solutions to overcome these challenges. This series is designed as a part of SolarTwins Project Joint Research Line 9: Social Aspects of Sustainable Energy Transitions

About SolarTwins: SolarTwins is a European Union Horizon 2020 (H2020) project coordinated by ODTÜ-GÜNAM through METU with CIEMAT-PSA (Spain) and DLR (Germany) as partners. The objectives of the SolarTwins project are to

1. Step-up the scientific excellence of the Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) Research Division ODAK of ODTÜ-GÜNAM through capacity building activities in collaboration with the globally leading CST institutions CIEMAT-PSA and DLR.
2. Strengthen METU, ODTÜ-GÜNAM, and Turkey's horizontal Research and Innovation (R&I) Capacities.

About METU TEKPOL: Science and Technology Policy Studies (STPS) program was founded in 1997 at the Middle East Technical University with the explicit objective to supply science and technology policy related human capital for the government bodies, agencies and other related organizations and to conduct research in science, technology and innovation policy issues. It has organic relations with the Research Center for Science and Technology Policies. Education and research elements integrate under METU-TEKPOL. TEKPOL is the only academic unit in Turkey that concurrently coordinates education and research activities. It operates M.Sc. and Ph.D. programs in science technology policy studies at the Graduate School of Social Sciences. TEKPOL also conducts interdisciplinary research on science and technology policy issues with the aim of addressing societal challenges.

PROGRAMME:

Date	Speaker, Institution	Seminar Title
15 April 2022	Arda MEVLÜTOĞLU, Kubilay YILDIRIM and Semih AKÇOMAK	TOGG and Beyond (in Turkish) – Panel
22 April 2022	Onur Çağdaş ARTANTAŞ	Promotion of Green Electricity: Legal and Political Perspectives (in Turkish)
29 April 2022	Serdar TÜRKELİ	Technological change and non-intervention, novel indicators and non-measurement (in Turkish)
13 May 2022	Barbel EPP	Cost Trends for Commercial and Industrial Solar Heat
20 May 2022	Pınar DERİN GÜRE	Gender and social sciences involvement in technology development projects in energy (in Turkish)
27 May 2022	Şuhnaz YILMAZ ÖZBAĞCI	Sustainable Energy and Climate Policies in the Light of Changing Global and Regional Dynamics (in Turkish)
3 June 2022	Derek BAKER	ODAKTR: Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) as a key enabling technology for Turkey's Clean Energy Transition.
10 June 2022	Christian OLTRA	Introducing SSH aspects of Energy Transitions
17 June 2022	S. Banu AKKAŞ, Zela ÖZDEMİR	METU in New European Research Area (in Turkish)
24 June 2022	Seven AĞIR	Sustainability and AgroPV Potential in Turkish Agriculture From Social Sciences Perspective

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